

Polarographic Studies of Cadmium γ -Picoline Complexes in Aqueous and Aqueous-Methanol Mixtures

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Pyridine forms weak complexes with zinc and cadmium as reported by Sharma and Gaur¹, but it was found from a survey of literature that complexes of substituted pyridine have received little attention. Bruhlman and Verhock² studies the α - and γ -picoline complexes of Ag^+ and γ -picoline complexes of Cu^{2+} . Murmann and Basalo³ have investigated the β - and γ -picoline complexes of Ag^+ by *pH* titration method, using a glass electrode. Polarography of γ -picoline complexes in aqueous, and aqueous-organic solvents has not been reported. The present paper deals with the determination of composition and stability constants of cadmium γ -picoline complexes in aqueous, 25%, 50% and 75% aqueous methanol (by volume) solutions by polarographic method. Above 75% of methanol, the experiments could not be performed because of the insolubility of potassium nitrate.

EXPERIMENTAL

PO_4 automatic pen recording Radiometer (Copenhagen) was used. The dropping mercury electrode had the following characteristics : $m = 1.8 \text{ mg/sec.}$, $t = 4.3 \text{ sec.}$ (at -0.8 V. vs. S.C.E. in $0.1M \text{ KNO}_3$).

FIG. 1. PLOTS OF $E_{1/2}$ VS. $-\text{LOG } C_x$ FOR CADMIUM- γ -PICOLINE SYSTEM IN AQUEOUS METHANOL [O] AQUEOUS, [□] 25% [△] 50%, [X] 75%.

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Reagent grade chemicals were used. Solutions containing 0.75 mM cadmium and different concentrations of γ -picoline (0.1M to 0.7M) in 0.1M KNO_3 were prepared. Triton $\times 100$ (0.001 per cent) was used as maxima suppressor. Purified nitrogen presaturated with the solution to be polarographed, was used for removing oxygen from the solutions.

Theory : It has been shown by DeFord and Hume⁵ that the shift in half-wave potential due to complex formation can be expressed as

$$\Delta E_{\frac{1}{2}} = (E_{\frac{1}{2}})_s - (E_{\frac{1}{2}})_c = \frac{2.303 RT}{nF} \log_{10} \gamma_M \frac{I_c}{I_s} \sum_0^N \frac{\beta_j \{X\}^j}{\gamma_{MX_j}} \quad \dots (1)$$

where $(E_{\frac{1}{2}})_c$ and $(E_{\frac{1}{2}})_s$ are the half-wave potentials of the complex and simple metal ions respectively, R, T and F have their usual significance, n denotes the number of electrons involved in the reduction, I_s and I_c are the experimental diffusion currents for the simple

FIG.2 F_j ([X]) PLOTS FOR CADMIUM- γ -PICOLINE SYSTEM IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM AND DOTTED LINE (---) FOR 25% METHANOL

and complex ions respectively, β_j is the overall formation constant of the j th complex; $\{X\}$ is the activity of the complexing ligand and γ_M and γ_{MX_j} denote the activity coefficients, at the electrode surface, of the metal and complex species respectively. Equation (1) can be rearranged to define a function $F_0([X])$

$$F_0([X]) = \text{antilog}_{10} \left[\frac{0.4343nF}{RT} \Delta E_{\frac{1}{2}} + \log \frac{I_s}{I_c} \right] = \gamma_M \sum_0^N \frac{\beta_j [X]^j}{\gamma_{MX_j}}$$

$$= 1 + \beta_1 [X] \frac{\gamma_M \gamma_X}{\gamma_{MX_1}} + \beta_2 [X]^2 \frac{\gamma_M (\gamma_X)^2}{\gamma_{MX_2}} + \dots \quad \dots (2)$$

Equation (2) can be written in the forms (3), (4) and (5) if the ionic strength is kept constant and the activity coefficients are taken as also being constant

$$F_1([X]) = \{F_0([X]) - 1\} / [X] = \beta_1 + \beta_2[X] + B_3[X]^2 \quad \dots (3)$$

$$F_2([X]) = \{F_1([X]) - \beta_1\} / [X] = \beta_2 + \beta_3[X] \quad \dots (4)$$

$$F_3([X]) = \{F_2([X]) - \beta_2\} / [X] = \beta_3 + \beta_4[X] \quad \dots (5)$$

where $[X]$ denotes the concentration of the complexing ligand, and γ the activity coefficient of the species indicated by the subscript. β_1 , β_2 and β_3 are the overall formation constants for the complexes containing one, two and three ligands respectively. Values of $F_0([X])$ for various concentrations of the complexing ligand can be determined experimentally and equation (2) can then be solved graphically for β_1 , β_2 and β_3 .

The proportion of the uncomplexed metal ion and the various complex species as a function of the ligand concentration can be calculated by means of the equations

$$\frac{M}{C_M} = \frac{1}{F_0([X])} \quad \dots (6)$$

$$\frac{MX_j}{C_M} = \frac{\beta_j [X]^j}{F_0([X])} \quad \dots (7)$$

where M denotes the concentration of uncomplexed metal ions, MX_j is the concentration of the j th complex and C_M is the total concentration of metal ion added to the system.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In each case a single well-defined reduction wave appeared. The reduction of cadmium in γ -picoline was found to be reversible and diffusion controlled. The plots of $\log \frac{i}{i_d - i}$ vs $E_{d.e.}$ were found to be linear with slope of 32 ± 2 mV.

FIG. 3 $F_j([X])$ PLOTS FOR CADMIUM γ -PICOLINE SYSTEM IN 50% METHANOL (—) AND 75% METHANOL (---)

The plots of E_1 vs $-\log C_X$ (Fig. 1) were found to be straight lines in all systems. The value of coordination number p is 2, obtained by the relation

$$\frac{\Delta E_1}{\Delta \log C_X} = \frac{-p}{n} 0.0601,$$

indicated the presence of $\text{Cd}(\gamma\text{-picol})_2^{2+}$ in every system. The value of stability constants ($\log \beta_2$) are 3.0, 2.76, 2.75 and 2.40 in aqueous, 25%, 50% and 75% aqueous-methanol solutions respectively as determined by Lingane⁴ method.

DeFord and Hume's⁵ method as modified by Irving⁶ was applied to determine the composition and stepwise formation constants of the complexes, by graphical extrapolation of $F_j([X])$ functions against C_X (Figs. 2 & 3).

The values of the overall formation constants from figs. 2 to 4 are as follows:

Stability constant	Aqueous	25%	50%	75%
β_1	50	60	20	15
β_2	1000	910	730	225

The percentage distribution of cadmium present in various forms as a function of the logarithm of ligand concentration was calculated by equation (6) and (7) and shown in figure 4.

FIG. 4. PERCENTAGE COMPOSITION OF VARIOUS SPECIES IN CADMIUM- γ -PICOLINE SYSTEM (AQUEOUS) (—) AND IN 25% METHANOL (---)

As reduction is diffusion controlled, cadmium can be estimated polarographically in γ -picoline solution.

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